

IRRN GUIDELINES

The *International Rice Research Newsletter* objective is:

“To expedite communication among scientists concerned with the development of improved technology for rice and for rice-based cropping systems. This publication will report what scientists are doing to increase the production of rice, inasmuch as this crop feeds the most densely populated and land-scarce nations in the world . . . IRRN is a mechanism to help rice scientists keep each other informed of current research findings.”

The concise reports contained in IRRN are meant to encourage rice scientists and workers to communicate with one another. In this way, readers can obtain more detailed information on the research reported.

Please examine the criteria, guidelines, and research categories that follow.

If you have comments or suggestions, please write the editor, IRRN, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. We look forward to your continuing interest in IRRN.

Criteria for IRRN research report

- has international, or pan-national, relevance
- has rice environment relevance
- advances rice knowledge
- uses appropriate research design and data collection methodology
- reports appropriate, adequate data
- applies appropriate analysis, using appropriate statistical techniques
- reaches supportable conclusions

Guidelines for contributors

The International Rice Research Newsletter is a compilation of brief reports of current research on topics of interest to rice scientists all over the world. Contributions should be reports of recent work and work-in-progress that have broad, pan-national interest and application. Only reports of work conducted during the immediate past three years should be submitted.

Research reported in IRRN should be verified. Single season, single trial field experiments are not accepted. All field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location, as appropriate. All experiments should include replication and a check or control treatment.

All work should have pan-national relevance.

Reports of routine screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, and cropping methods using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not accepted.

Normally, no more than one report will be accepted from a single experiment. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submission at different times of multiple reports from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection of such submissions will result in rejection of all.

Please observe the following guidelines in preparing submissions:

- Limit each report to two pages of double-spaced typewritten text and no more than two figures (graphs, tables, or photos).
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.
- Organize the report into a brief statement of research objectives, a brief description of project design, and a brief discussion of results. Relate results to the objectives.
- Report appropriate statistical analysis.
- Specify the rice production environment (irrigated, rainfed lowland, upland, deepwater, tidal wetlands).

- Specify the type of rice culture (transplanted, wet seeded, dry seeded).
- Specify seasons by characteristic weather (wet season, dry season, monsoon) and by months. Do not use local terms for seasons or, if used, define them.
- Use standard, internationally recognized terms to describe rice plant parts, growth stages, environments, management practices, etc. Do not use local names.
- Provide genetic background for new varieties or breeding lines.
- For soil nutrient studies, be sure to include a standard soil profile description, classification, and relevant soil properties.
- Provide scientific names for diseases, insects, weeds, and crop plants. Do not use common names or local names alone.
- Quantify survey data (infection percentage, degree of severity, sampling base, etc.).
- When evaluating susceptibility, resistance, tolerance, etc., report the actual quantification of damage due to stress that was used to assess level or incidence. Specify the measurements used.
- Use generic names, not trade names, for all chemicals.
- Use international measurements. Do not use local units of measure. Express yield data in metric tons per hectare (t/ha) for field studies and in grams per pot (g/pot) or per specified length (in meters) row (g/row) for small scale studies.
- Express all economic data in terms of the US\$. Do not use local monetary units. Economic information should be presented at the exchange rate US\$:local currency at the time data were collected.
- When using acronyms or abbreviations, write the name in full on first mention, followed by the acronym or abbreviation in parentheses. Thereafter, use the abbreviation.
- Define any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or graph in a footnote or caption/legend.

Categories of research published

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT
genetic resources
genetics
breeding methods
yield potential
grain quality
pest resistance
diseases
insects
other pests
stress tolerance
drought
excess water
adverse temperature
adverse soils
integrated germplasm improvement
irrigated
rainfed lowland
upland
deepwater
tidal wetlands
seed technology

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT
soils
soil microbiology
physiology and plant nutrition
fertilizer management
inorganic sources
organic sources
crop management
integrated pest management
diseases
insects
weeds
other pests
water management
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nurse cells (20 mg/ml). Suspension cultures of Oc cell line from Dr. K. Syono of the University of Tokyo were used as nurse cells. Nurse cells were removed after 10 d and the liquid was replaced with the same amount of fresh medium. Under the inverted microscope, the cultures were observed periodically for colony formation. The number of colony-producing protoplasts was recorded 4 wk after plating.

Semisolid N₆ medium consisting of 0.6% agarose VII wt/vol and 2 mg 2,4-D/

liter was tested with sucrose and maltose as the C source. The protoplasts remained viable (with cytoplasmic streaming and changes in shape) for a longer time (3-5 d) in maltose than in sucrose (1-2 d).

We used maltose as the C source when we tested series of semisolid N₆ media. Maltose (13% wt/vol) was found to be the best osmotic concentration for protoplast culture (Table 1). Many cellular divisions and some colonies were

observed 28 d after plating.

To evaluate the efficiency of colony formation, the N₆ medium with 13% maltose was modified using 0.6% agarose VII and 0.5% sea plaque agarose. Both media gave about the same hardness. The plating efficiency was higher in medium with sea plaque agarose (Table 2).

So far, initial attempts to regenerate green plants from protoplast-derived calli have produced only green points. □

Low-light-adapted restorers of different maturity durations for hybrid rice breeding

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Low light levels during the critical reproductive and ripening phases adversely affect rice productivity. Heterotic hybrid combinations with restorers adapted to low light can improve productivity during the wet season (WS).

We studied the low light adaptability of 39 recently purified restorers of elite rice varieties with maturity durations of early (111-120 d), early to medium (121-130 d), medium (131-140 d), and late (more than 141 d). Wooden screens shaded the plants in the field and provided 50% sunlight from 40 d after planting to harvest. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (340 cal/cm² per d).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design. Yield, total dry matter (TDM), and harvest index (HI) were recorded at harvest.

The low light reduced mean TDM by 63%, yield 75%, and HI 36% (see table). The extent of reduction, however, was least in the late-maturing group and most in the early to medium group. TDM, yield, and HI were high—specially under low light—iRtb 10, IR50 (early); Swarnaprabha, IR64 R (early to medium); IR19058-107-1, Vajram, ARC11353 (medium); and Jagannath and Mahsuri (late). These restorers also

The effect of low light (50% of normal) from 40 d after planting to harvest on yield, TDM, and HI of restorers with varying maturity durations. Cuttack, India, 1991 wet season.

Restorer	Yield (g/m ²)		TDM (g/m ²)		HI (%)	
	Light	Shade	Light	Shade	Light	Shade
Early (111-120 d)						
IR58	437	83	825	286	53	29
WGL3962	413	61	831	206	49	27
IR50	369	113	733	315	50	36
Ptb 10	347	202	669	452	52	45
IR50 R	342	91	701	280	48	32
Prasad	338	44	683	175	49	25
HKR120	334	77	773	303	42	26
IET6155	323	67	620	194	52	34
Semaigincha	320	77	760	233	55	33
IR339515-8-1-1	300	58	602	184	49	32
WGL 3935	256	36	635	194	40	17
IR22107-120-1	231	41	494	144	47	28
Early to medium (121-130 d)						
Swarnaprabha ^a	567	142	1167	481	49	28
IR64 R	392	102	936	350	41	30
Suweon 318	379	38	860	191	44	20
Tellahdmsa	368	32	786	208	49	15
HKR119	365	80	809	242	45	33
IR64	352	61	773	219	46	28
IR36	351	64	133	238	43	27
Suweon 332	338	48	727	198	46	25
Suweon 294	325	68	736	229	44	30
Pusa 702 R	321	74	683	248	47	31
Pusa 205 R	313	40	856	221	36	17
Suweon 325	261	36	590	157	44	23
Milyang 54	235	32	657	164	36	21
Ratna ^a	223	17	681	177	34	17
Medium (131-140 d)						
Vajram	560	150	1409	473	40	34
ARC11353	421	138	1027	488	40	26
IR54	363	111	1094	464	33	23
IR19058-107-1	337	158	1227	595	27	27
Indira ^a	257	56	1047	262	25	19
IR2731.5-145-1-3	257	86	937	470	26	19
Indrasan	249	86	581	289	43	28
IR4422-480-2-3-3	191	24	719	171	26	14
Late (more than 141 d)						
Jagannath	576	219	1366	656	42	33
Mahsuri	475	187	1283	677	37	27
Savitri	469	158	1447	679	49	32
Samalei	460	168	1419	601	32	28
Swama	433	186	1106	523	39	36
LSD (0.05)	162	58	226	129	11	ns
Means						
111-120 d	334	79	694	247	49	30
121-130 d	342	60	785	237	43	25
131-140 d	329	100	1005	401	33	24
>141 d	483	184	1324	627	40	36
General mean	355	90	871	3	2442	27

^aPartial restorer.

effect between photoperiod and temperature could be adapted to wider areas because a high temperature can complement the insufficiency of

photoperiod in low latitudes and a longer photoperiod can complement the inefficiency of temperature in high latitudes. The ideal type of sterile line for

hybrid rice production has a low CFP, a high CSP, a wide TRPS, and a high intensity of supplementary effect between light and temperature. □

The relationship of photosensitivity and sterility in photosensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) lines

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PGMS rice was first discovered in a field of Nongken 58S, a photoperiod-sensitive japonica variety. Photoperiod controls both the development and the pollen fertility of Nongken 58S. Most PGMS lines were photoperiod-sensitive; photoperiod-insensitive sterile lines derived from Nongken 58S became thermosensitive sterile lines. We wanted to breed PGMS lines that are photoperiod insensitive to flowering induction.

We crossed Mudanjiang 8, a photoperiod-insensitive variety, with Nongken 58S. We selected sterile plants with short growth durations from the F₂. From the F₉, we selected the sterile line E85S. We planted it and its parents in 1990 under short day (SD) 10 h light/d, and long day (LD) 14.5 h light/d conditions to observe growth duration and pollen fertility percent (see table).

E85S is insensitive to photoperiod for flowering induction as is Mudanjiang 8, and is sensitive to photoperiod in its fertility alteration, like Nongken 58S. These results indicate that different genes control photosensitive sterility and photosensitive flowering induction and they can be recombined in new types of PGMS lines. □

Fertility and photosensitivity of E85S and its parents. China, 1991.

	Nongken 58S	Mudanjiang 8	E85S
SD heading promotion rate ^a	38.5	-3.4	2.0
Photoperiod sensitivity	Strong	Weak	Weak
Days from sowing to heading with at least 14.5 h of light/d	104	59	58
Maturity type	Late	Early	Early
Fertile pollen (%)			
In SD	70.2	77.4	65.6
In LD	0.0	76.8	0.0

$$^a\text{SD heading promotion rate} = \frac{d \text{ from sowing to heading in LD} - d \text{ from sowing to heading in SD}}{d \text{ from sowing to heading in LD}} \times 100.$$

Identification of CMS lines for hybrid rice development under northern Indian conditions

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We evaluated 13 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines for adaptability and stability for pollen sterility under the subhumid tropical conditions of western UP in northern India. V20 A, which originated from China, and IR62829 A and IR58025 A, which originated from IRRI, were obtained from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad. PMS-1 through PMS-10 originated from Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Kapurthala. We planted 5-row plots of each line on 16 Jul 1991 under strict isolation, using *Sesbania* spp. as a physical barrier. Data were recorded for

Performance of CMS lines at Pantnagar, India, during 1991 wet season.

CMS line	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Stability
V20 A	81	72.6	100.0	100.0	Stable
IR62829 A	93	71.7	99.7	99.1	Needs purification
IR58025 A	99	81.0	100.0	99.9	Stable
PMS-1	109	64.1	100.0	100.0	Stable
PMS-2	102	63.6	100.0	99.7	Stable
PMS-3	109	70.8	98.4	99.9	Unstable
PMS-4	113	64.8	99.4	99.9	Needs purification
PMS-5	113	66.0	100.0	100.0	Stable
PMS-6	114	66.2	98.1	100.0	Unstable
PMS-7	109	74.6	95.1	100.0	Unstable
PMS-8	109	64.4	100.0	99.9	Stable
PMS-9	113	79.0	86.2	100.0	Unstable
PMS-10	107	69.5	100.0	100.0	Stable

days to 50% flowering, plant height, percent pollen sterility, and percent spikelet fertility, for which we used the mean of 25 panicles.

We identified several stable CMS lines with varying duration and plant type (see table). V20 A, IR58025 A, PMS-1 A, PMS-2 A, PMS-5 A, PMS-8 A, and PMS-10 A had complete pollen sterility and almost 100% spikelet sterility. In

contrast with earlier observations, IR62829 A had slight fertility of pollen and spikelets, possibly because of a different seed source.

These stable lines all had very short stature (63.6-72.6 cm), except IR58025 A, which had semidwarf stature (81.0 cm). V20 A had early duration, IR58025 A and PMS-2 mid-early, and others, medium to mid-late. Observations at

The soil is fine loam overlying silty loam and deep gravel. Vegetation is predominantly *Imperata cylindrica* with *Ophiuros* spp. and *Digitaria* spp. Annual rainfall averages 1,400 mm.

We dibbled 5-6 seeds/hill at 20- × 20-cm spacing, keeping sowing depth uniform. Each genotype was planted on 15 m². The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design with five replications. We recorded yield data for 100 hills (4 m² net area)/genotype per replication and yield components for 20 hills/genotype per replication. Data from only three of the replications showed consistency and were used for analysis of variance.

Tambu, Wantok, Niupela, NG8313, and NG8315 significantly outyielded the other genotypes (see table). They also

Yield and yield components of rice varieties under upland field condition in Gaidusen, Markham Valley, Morobe Province, PNG, 1991.^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Panicle fertility (%)	Harvest index (%)	1000-grain wt (g)
Tambu	2.4 a	70.3 a	20.4 a	21.8 a	44.1 e	39.5 b	0.5 e	16.0 c
Wantok	2.3 a	70.6 b	19.7 a	21.0 a	42.7 c	41.3 b	0.4 e	17.2 c
Niupela	2.7 a	112.5 a	11.5 c	22.5 a	73.7 a	50.9 a	0.5 e	13.7 d
Senis	1.2 b	74.6 b	12.6 b	21.4 a	26.8 d	23.5 d	0.6 d	15.9 c
BR12-5-5-1-1	0.6 c	71.7 b	16.6 b	21.2 a	38.6 c	46.9 a	0.4 e	14.2 d
NG8297	1.1 b	74.2 b	15.5 b	21.2 a	32.1 d	31.5 c	0.7 c	17.2 c
NG8304	1.2 b	73.1 b	14.2 b	20.1 a	28.1 d	29.0 c	0.9 c	19.1 b
NG8313	2.7 a	82.1 b	24.0 a	20.1 a	58.1 b	49.5 a	1.7 a	16.5 c
NG8315	2.4 a	58.1 c	19.3 a	20.1 a	21.2 e	22.4 d	1.8 a	24.7 a
NG8321	1.5 b	58.2 c	11.0 c	20.7 a	31.5 d	39.7 b	1.2 b	19.4 b
CV (%)	14.5							

^a In a column, figures followed by different letters significantly differ at the 5% level by DMRT.

outperformed the others in yield components, such as productive tillers/hill, filled grains/panicle, harvest index, and 1,000-grain weight.

These genotypes will be tested in different agroecological zones before they are recommended for general cultivation in the country. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Reaction of rice genotypes of different origins and genealogy to blast (B1) disease in Nigeria

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Rice B1 *Pyricularia grisea* is a major constraint to rice production in Africa. Its severity is greatest in the uplands, rainfed lowlands, and inland valleys of West Africa and in the cold-prone mid-altitude areas in the East, Central, and Southern Africa sub-region.

We screened 1,253 lines and best local check varieties for reaction to B1 at an upland site at IITA, (7° N, 3° E, and 200 m above sea level) with reliably high B1 levels. The lines were entries in various INGER-Africa nurseries in 1991 and in the International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN). The B1 screening plot was laid out to conform with the IRBN plot design.

Analysis of *Standard evaluation system for rice* B1 score data revealed that of the 266 entries in the upland nurseries,

Adapted upland rice varieties common in the ancestry of B1-resistant lines.^a

Variety	Origin	Lines developed (no.)
<i>Adapted varieties or progenitor</i>		
Colombia 1	Colombia	32
Dourado Precoce	Brazil	18
Eloni	Surinam	17
Iguape Cateto	Brazil	12
LAC23	Liberia	8
Moroberekan	West Africa	17
OS6	Zaire	7
Palawan	Philippines	14
63-83	Cote d'Ivoire	19
<i>Modern varieties</i>		
IAC25	Brazil	12
IR13149-19-1	IIRI	9
IRAT104	Cote d'Ivoire	21
IRAT112	Cote d'Ivoire	12
IRAT113	Cote d'Ivoire	34
IRAT212	IITA	17
ITA235	IITA	10
M312A	Cote d'Ivoire	32
TOx7	IITA	8
TOx1010	IITA	19
TOx1367-7	IITA	15
TOx1780	IITA	8
Total		341

^a Of 1,253 entries screened, 580 were recorded as B1 resistant. Among these, more than 59% were derived from the adapted varieties listed above.

145 scored 0-1 and only four scored 7-9. Of the 268 entries in the irrigated nurseries, 24 scored 0-1 and 55 scored 7-9. Of the 539 entries in both African and global B1 nurseries, 108 scored 0-1 and 110 scored 7-9.

Most entries in the irrigated and rainfed lowland nurseries had intermediate scores of 4-6 (see figure, a). In the upland nurseries, however, entries with scores of 0-3 had the highest frequency. Similarly, many entries in the

The two glutinous rice varieties Black Puttu and White Puttu, both with tall plant stature, recorded 2.5 and 1.7 t/ha, respectively (see table). Both Jeeraga Samba types are characterized by low rough rice weight and moderate yield

potential. Dwarf-statured, nonlodging varieties IET8580 (Kasthuri) and IET10364 (Pusa Basmati 1) have brown rice, length of more than 7 mm, and an L:B ratio of about 4. They possess good yield potential. IET8580 is strongly

scented; IET10364 is lightly scented.

The superiority of Pusa Basmati 1 was revealed in this study. It is being used as donor in the breeding program to improve aromatic and quality rice varieties in Tamil Nadu. □

Performance of quality rice varieties at TRRI, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Pedigree	Duration (d)	Plant ht at maturity (cm)	Yield (t/ha)	1000-grain wt ^a (g)	Brown rice			Shape ^b	Scent ^c
						Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)	L:B		
Black Puttu	Local	134	131	2.5	21.2	6.9	2.0	3.5	S	0
White Puttu	Local	144	134	1.7	23.8	7.0	2.5	2.8	M	0
AEB148	Jeeraga Samba-nonscented	140	137	1.5	10.2	4.5	2.2	2.0	B	0
AEB178	Jeeraga Samba-scented	140	140	1.7	10.0	4.4	2.2	2.0	B	2
Sugadas	Local	142	142	2.0	21.0	6.7	2.7	2.5	M	1
Rascadam	Local	135	145	1.1	11.4	4.3	2.3	1.9	B	1
HBC19	Karnal Local	141	109	0.8	20.8	7.7	1.8	4.3	S	1
Basmati 370	Local	141	110	1.8	21.5	7.5	1.9	3.9	S	1
IET8580 (Kasthuri)	Basmati 370/CR88-17-1-5	139	103	1.9	20.8	7.3	1.9	3.8	S	1
IET10364 (Pusa Basmati 1)	Pusa 167/Karnal Local	134	88	2.4	18.4	7.4	1.8	4.1	S	2

^aRough rice basis. ^bS = slender, M = medium, B = bold. ^c0 = nonscented, 1 = lightly scented, 2 = scented. Based on SES.

Effect of plant density on rice grain quality

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We tested three levels of plant densities—118, 560, 160, 550, and 197,600 plants/ha—for Basmati 385 and advanced line 4048 during 1989-90 and 1990-91 cropping seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications in 4- × 6-m plots. Data were averaged.

Thousand-grain weight, cooked grain length, total milling recovery, head rice recovery, and protein content decreased as plant densities of both varieties

increased (see table). The effect of plant density on kernel dimension, amylose content, and gel length was not consistent. □

Effect of plant density on grain quality parameters, 1989-90, 1990-91.^a

Quality character	Basmati 385			Basmati line 4048		
	118,560	160,550	197,600	118,560	160,550	197,600
Grain length (mm)	6.75 a	6.74 a	6.72 a	7.28 a	7.29 a	7.19 b
Grain width (mm)	1.63 a	1.60 a	1.60 a	1.60 a	1.62 a	1.60 a
1000-grain wt (g)	15.02 a	14.84 a	14.69 a	16.28 a	16.11 b	15.41 c
Cooked grain length (mm)	13.50 a	13.30 b	13.10 c	13.95 a	13.75 a	13.45 b
Total milled rice (%)	70.40 a	70.00 a	69.60 a	70.30 a	69.80 a	69.00 b
Head rice (%)	54.60 a	53.00 ab	51.43 b	52.70 a	50.90 b	48.00 c
Bursting of grains upon cooking (%)	6.50 a	8.33 a	9.17 a	4.50 a	4.60 a	5.50 a
Protein content (%)	9.10 a	8.70 a	8.40 a	8.90 a	8.60 a	8.40 a
Amylose content (%)	25.00 a	24.90 a	24.90 a	23.70 b	23.70 b	24.90 a
Gel length (mm)	67.50 b	65.60 b	84.50 a	66.50 b	65.10 b	79.00 a

^aValues in a row followed by a common letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level by DMRT.

Comparison of grain quality of mechanically and hand-harvested rice

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Combine harvesters are becoming popular in Punjab, Pakistan, because of the shortage of farm labor during the peak harvest season.

From 15 locations in Sahiwal, Okara, and Kasur districts, we collected samples of KS282 (medium-grain) and Basmati

Grain quality of mechanically harvested and hand-harvested rice.^a

Character ^b	KS282		Basmati 198	
	Mechanically harvested	Hand-harvested	Mechanically harvested	Hand-harvested
Moisture content (%)	29.7 a	20.2 b	30.5 a	21.0 b
Green and immature grains (%)	11.2 a	4.0 b	14.1 a	6.2 b
Production of husked grains (%)	2.1 a	0.0 b	3.2 a	0.0 b
Total milling recovery (% db)	69.8 b	71.5 a	68.7 b	70.0 a
Head rice recovery (% db)	54.2 b	58.1 a	50.0 b	55.0 a

^aIn a row, values followed by the same letter for each variety are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bdb = dry basis.

198 (fine-grain) that were harvested with a Ford New Holland model 8040 combine harvester. A small portion of

the same fields was harvested and grains threshed by hand for comparison. Results were averaged across locations.

Table 1. Photosynthetic rate (P_n) at flowering, total dry matter (TDM), yield, and harvest index (HI) of F_1 rice hybrids under normal light and low light (50% normal) from 40d to harvest. Cuttack, India, 1990 and 1991 wet seasons.

Hybrid	Flowering		Harvest					
	P_n (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)	$P_n \times LAI$ (gCO ₂ /m ² per h)	TDM (g/m ²)		Yield (g/m ²)		HI (%)	
			Light	Shade	Light	Shade	Light	Shade
<i>1990 wet season</i>								
V20 A/Milyang 46	27.2	8.3	693	362	318	62	45	17
V20 A/IR36	31.1	8.4	634	346	209	102	33	29
IR54752 A/IR54	34.1	13.4	1201	483	413	159	34	33
IR54752 A/IR46	28.4	10.8	1115	497	343	83	31	17
IR54752 A/Vajram	36.1	14.3	1276	670	537	285	42	42
IR54752 A/Swarna	32.1	13.5	1041	393	345	73	33	18
Intan Mutant A/ARC11353	31.5	10.6	960	583	127	37	13	6
Intan Mutant A/IR27315	34.1	10.8	947	468	169	110	18	23
Swarnaprabha (check)	31.4	10.7	1146	619	537	231	47	37
Mean	31.8	11.2	1001	491	333	127	33	25
LSD (0.05)								
Hybrid (H)	2.1	1.2		23		25		—
Treatment (T)	—	—		54		41		—
H at same T	—	—		32		36		—
T at same H	—	—		48		36		—
<i>1991 wet season</i>								
IR62829 A/WGL	392543.7	11.3	794	181	383	29	49	16
IR62829 A/WGL	396232.0	9.1	817	274	434	84	53	30
IR62829 A/Swarna	42.0	17.4	1117	313	473	46	42	14
IR62829 A/Vajram	56.3	19.0	1187	448	536	140	45	31
IR62829 A/IR36	42.9	13.9	680	170	286	33	42	19
IR62829 Anellahamsa	47.6	11.6	811	286	345	55	43	18
Swarnaprabha	54.8	19.3	1167	481	567	142	49	28
Mean	45.6	14.5	939	308	432	76	46	22
LSD (0.05)								
Hybrid (H)	3.2	1.4		128		67		—
Treatment (T)	—	—		42		63		—
H at same T	—	—		181		94		—
T at same H	—	—		187		136		—

the Sugarcane Research Station, Vuyyuru, when it was grown after sugarcane in a well-drained fertile soil. Heterosis in yield over the pollen parent Vajram and standard heterosis over the best local check MTU 9992 were apparent (Table 2).

IR62829 A/Vajram, with 125-130 d total duration, was bred at Agricultural Research Station, Maruteru, in the coastal monsoon belt of Andhra Pradesh, India. The hybrid has potential for use in the low-light monsoon areas. □

Table 2. Grain yield and heterosis in yield over the pollen parent of rice hybrids. Vuyyuru, Andhra Pradesh, India, 1991 WS.

Hybrid	Yield (g/m ²)	Heterosis over pollen parents
IR62829 A/WGL 3925	520	-9
IR62829 A/WGL 3962	442	-23
IR62829 A/Swarna	698	-11
IR62829 A/Vajram	831	19
IR62829 A/IR36	594	-2
IR62829 A/Tellahamsa	542	13
MTU9992 (check)	636	—
LSD (0.05)	120	

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Genetic variation of chlorophyll synthesis of etiolated Nepalese rice seedlings at low temperature: a new approach for cold tolerance screening

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Cold injury is a major constraint to improving rice production in the hills of Nepal because it limits both the rice-producing area and the growing season length. Many screening techniques for cold tolerance in rice at germination and early growth stages have been reported in the literature. We tested a new approach for cold tolerance screening by exposing etiolated leaf tissue of cold-sensitive

Comparative chlorophyll synthesis at 17°C among Nepalese indigenous and exotic rice genotypes.

Genotype	Field ranking ^a	Total chlorophyll (a+b) (µg)	Plumule color ^b (1-9 scale)
Sinjali	CT	0.151	1
Silange	CT	0.061	3
Chhomrong	CT (check)	0.061	3
Takmare	CT	0.048	3
China 1039	CT	0.037	3
Raksali	CT	0.033	3
Palung 2	CT	0.032	3
Bhatte	CT	0.025	5
IR20	CS	0.025	5
Seto Bhakunde	CT	0.024	5
Marshi	CS	0.021	5
Darmali	CT	0.019	7
Kalopatlle	CT	0.019	7
Juwari	CS	0.008	7
IR8	CS	0.002	9
IR36	CS (check)	0.001	9

r vs total chlorophyll content — -0.772**

^aCT = cold tolerant. CS = cold susceptible. ^bPlumule color (1 - 9 scale) 1 = dark green, 3 = light green, 5 = pale, 7 = tinge of greenness, and 9 = white.

species—including indicas—to low temperature (17°C). Within 24 h, the tissue shows variation in the rate of chlorophyll synthesis. The more cold-tolerant species are thus easily identified

Using the etiolated seedling approach we assessed 16 rice genotypes, including 10 indigenous cold-tolerant rices and 2 cold-susceptible rices for ability to synthesize chlorophyll at low temperature.

After breaking seed dormancy with heat treatment in a dry air oven at 50°C for 5 d, groups of 50 seeds were soaked in aerated distilled water for 24 h and placed in petri dishes on wet filter papers at 25°C for 3 d in the dark. They were then transferred—still in the dark—to 7°C for 24 h of acclimation followed by 48 h in a 10/14 h day/night cycle. We determined the extent of greening by spectrophotometrically measuring the total

which they are induced. Elucidating the functions of these proteins can lead to understanding the mechanism underlying salt tolerance. These proteins may also offer a convenient tool for molecular screening of germplasm. □

Variability in salt tolerance of accessions of wild rice species *Oryza punctata* and *O. officinalis*

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We have started a comprehensive salt tolerance screening program for all available wild rice germplasm. In the first phase, six accessions of *O. punctata*—three diploid ($2n=2x=24$ BB) and three tetraploid ($2n=4x=48$ BBCC)—and three diploid accessions of *O. officinalis* ($2n=2x=24$ CC) were tested in the glasshouse. We used the gravel culture technique and natural conditions of temperature (25/15 °C day/night temperature), 10 h light, and 60% relative humidity.

We raised seedlings by planting internode cuttings of stems in plastic pots filled with gravel and Hoagland nutrient solution. The pots were placed in another plastic pot containing nutrient solution to ensure a continuous nutrient supply to the plant and easy replacement of the solution. We planted three cuttings per pot and three pots/accession per species.

When leaves started to appear, we induced artificial salinity with a mixture

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

Details of salt tolerance screening of different accessions of 2 wild rice species at 5 periods of growth (2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 wk).

Species	Accession no.	Chromosome number and genome	Survival (% of control)				
			2	4	6	8	10
<i>O. punctata</i>	103897 ^a	$2n = 2x = 24$	0	0	0	0	0
<i>O. punctata</i>	103917	BB	66	66	0	0	0
<i>O. punctata</i>	103903 ^b		33	0	-	-	-
<i>O. punctata</i>	105158	$2n=4x=48$	100	100	66	66	66
<i>O. punctata</i>	101389	BBCC	100	100	100	66	33
<i>O. punctata</i>	101408		100	100	66	33	0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	103286	$2n=2x=24$	100	100	66	66	33
<i>O. officinalis</i>	104973 ^a	CC	0	0	0	0	0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	105322 ^b		33	33	33	0	0
Basmati 370	Susceptible check		0	0	0	0	0
Jhona 349	Tolerant check		100	33	-	-	-

^aMost of the plants died at EC 5-8 dS/m. ^bMost of the plants died at EC 10-11 dS/m.

of Na₂SO₄ CaCl₂, MgCl₂, and NaCl at a ratio of 10:5:1:4 through a stepwise increase in electrical conductivity of 2 dS/m every other day until EC reached 12 dS/m. The entire saline solution was replaced with fresh solution semiweekly.

Susceptible check Basmati 370 died at the onset of EC 8 dS/m; tolerant check Jhona 349 died after 4 wk of growth at EC 12 dS/m (see table). Of the three accessions of *O. officinalis*, 104973 died between EC 5-EC 8 dS/m, 105322 survived for 6 wk, and 103286 survived for 10 wk at EC 12 dS/m.

Of the diploid accessions of *O. punctata*, only 103917 survived for 4 wk, while all three tetraploid accessions survived beyond 8 wk at EC 12 dS/m.

Accession 105158 survived for more than 12 wk in EC 12 dS/m. The plant was still in the vegetative phase and had only one tiller, but was healthy and green. We are not certain whether the vegetative growth was stressed by the weather during May-Aug, which is hot and dry under local conditions and a dormant period for wild rice species, or by salinity.

The study did indicate, however, that if many wild rice accessions are screened for salt tolerance, tremendous variability can be anticipated, and this can be used for salt tolerance improvement of cultivated rice varieties. As far as we are aware, this is the first report of salt tolerance in wild rice species other than *Porteresia coarctata*. Further studies are in progress. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

PR110, a new bacterial blight (BB)-resistant rice variety for Punjab, India

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PR 106 is a predominant rice variety in the Punjab because of its high yield potential,

long slender grains, and duration that fits very well into a rice - wheat crop rotation. PR106 is, however, susceptible to BB, which is the most serious rice disease in the Punjab.

The State Variety Approval Committee has approved a new BB-resistant rice variety, PR110, for cultivation in the Punjab. PR110 was developed using the backcross

approach, with PR106 as recurrent parent. It inherited BB resistance from Patong 32, a tall photoperiod-sensitive variety from Malaysia. A dwarf homozygous BB-resistant F₃ line of TN1/Patong 32 was used as the female parent in the first cross with PR106, and followed by five recurrent backcrosses with PR106. PR110, from TN1/Patong 32//PR 106*⁶, was

CTH3 (Bili Mukthi), a white-grained, cold- and blast (BI)-tolerant rice for southern Karnataka, India

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About 0.3 million ha of rice is cultivated in southern Karnataka under both canal- and reservoir-irrigated conditions. Canal-irrigated rice is planted during Jun-Jul because of the assured, regulated release of stored water. But reservoir-fed rice can be planted only after the reservoirs are full. This delay normally leads to late planting — sometimes not until September.

Even the very early-maturing recommended varieties, when planted after mid-August, flower during November (winter) and do not perform well. For such conditions, the only suitable variety that has been recently released is Mukthi (CTH1), a red-grained rice that few farmers prefer.

CTH3, a new selection from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery planted at Bangalore during 1983 winter, was multiplied for seed during 1984 and tested in three locations within Karnataka. It can meet the demand for a white-grained, cold- and BI-tolerant variety, and can supplement Mukthi over large areas in the reservoir-irrigated winter rice belt.

CTH3 was obtained from IR9202-25-1-3, derived from TR2053-521-1-1/K116/KN-1B-361-1-8-6-9-1. The selection is 95 cm high, has medium bold grains, moderate tillering, and grows normally from germination to maturity in any season because of its cold and BI tolerance and photoperiod insensitivity.

It yielded OS-5.0 t grain/ha during normal season and 0.6 to 1.9 t grain/ha during winter compared with 0.02-1.1 t/ha for best checks Mangala and CH2 (both white-grained) under winter conditions.

The table summarizes the performance of CTH3 for 6 yr at Bangalore. Its leaf BI score of 2 and 2% neck BI are better than the 7 and 5% for susceptible variety Halubblu. The performance of CTH3 at

Performance of cold-tolerant varieties from 2 plantings (Sep, Oct) at Bangalore, India, 1985-86 to 1990-91.

Entry	Grain yield (t/ha)												Total mean (t/ha)	Increase (%)over CH2	Blast			
	1985-86		1986-87		1987-88	1988-89		1989-90		1990-91		Mean			Sep	Oct	Leaf ^a	Neck (%)
	Sep	Oct	Sep	Oct	Sep	Sep	Oct	Sep	Oct	Sep	Oct							
CTH1	2.3	1.7	4.9	3.5	3.9	1.3	1.5	1.4	2.0	1.4	2.6	2.0	2.3	107	2	0		
CTH3	1.2	0.6	5.0	1.9	1.8	0.5	0.9	1.8	1.0	0.7	1.9	1.0	1.5	28	2	2		
Checks																		
Mangala	0.3	0.1	3.6	0.7	1.4	0.5	0.0	1.1	1.1	0.6	1.3	0.4	0.8	—	2	2.4		
CH2	1.3	1.1	3.6	0.5	2.2	0.4	—	1.0	0.7	0.6	1.5	0.7	1.1		2	1.5		
LSD	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.1	ns	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2	—	—	—					
CV (%)	14.9	16.1	13.7	14.2	19.2	—	27.5	21.4	23.5	19.4	—	—	—					

^aScored using Standard evaluation system for rice (0-9).

Bangalore, Mandya, and Mudigere during 1985-91 and on private farms in Mysore district has confirmed its superiority in winter and high degree of BI tolerance.

It is now approved for farm trials in Karnataka in the hill zone and is spreading from farmer to farmer in Mysore district under the name Bili Mukthi. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed

TKM10, a new higher yielding rice for semidry conditions

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Rice is cultivated on about 45,000 ha under semidry conditions (rainfed lowland-subsequently irrigated) in Chengalpattu MGR district of Tamil Nadu, India.

Table 1. Overall yield performance of TKM10.

Trial	no.	Yield (t/ha)	
		TKM10	TKM1
Research Station			
Tirur	4	1.9	1.1
Adaptive research trial			
October 1989-90	28	2.0	1.7
Adaptive research trial			
October 1990-91	19	3.8	2.7
Mean		2.6	1.8

Table 2. Drought score at RSS, Tirur, Tamil Nadu, 1989-91.

Entry	Parentage	1989-90		1990-91	
		Tolerance	Recovery	Tolerance	Recovery
TKM 10	CO 31/C22	1	1	1	1
IR20	IR262/TKM6	5	5	3	5
TKM1	Pisini (local selection)	1	1	1	1
CO 31	GEB24/ <i>O. perennis</i>	1	1	1	1
IET 1444	TN1/CO 29	5	3	5	3
TKMY	TKM7/IR8	3	3	3	1

^aScored using SES.

TKM1, a local genotype released 30 yr ago as a pureline variety from Pisini, was previously the only suitable variety for this environment.

We initiated breeding work to develop a drought-tolerant, high-yielding semidry rice. This work resulted in the identification of elite culture TM8602, a hybrid derivative of the cross CO 31/C22, which was released as TKM 10. This culture is a semitall plant with nonlodging culms.

Trials conducted in both RRS and farmers' fields revealed the high-yielding potential of this genotype compared with check TKM1. TKM10 averaged 2.6 t grain/ha (Table 1) with a maximum yield of 5.2 t/ha recorded in a trial plot that received enough rainfall during sowing and vegetative and reproductive phases.

TKM10 matures in 135 d under direct seeding. Its seedlings, along with checks, were assessed for drought tolerance during the vegetative phase in 1989-90 and 1990-

SLW were significant independent variables ($P < 0.03$) for predicting leaf N concentration in both greenhouse and field studies. With three SPAD readings per leaf blade in each case, the proportion of variability in leaf N concentration that the independent variable accounted for increased from 81 to 86% in the greenhouse study and

from 74 to 78% in the field study when based on SPAD values alone vs the combination of SPAD values and SLW as independent variables (see table).

Using a chlorophyll meter to monitor the N status of the rice plant may provide a useful tool for managing research experiments and varietal trials where adequate N supply must be maintained in

diverse environments and on different soils. Data, however, should be interpreted with caution because the SLW can influence the SPAD reading. If leaf N estimates need to be more accurate than SPAD readings, then the SLW should also be determined. This process is much simpler and faster than using the kjeldahl method to determine N. □

Fertilizer management—**inorganic sources**

Nutrient management for cotton - rice cropping system

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Cotton *Gossypium hirsutum* L. is grown in Srivilliputtur during Feb-Mar under summer irrigated conditions following wet-season rice. A short-duration pulse is generally grown during Aug-Sep between the cotton and rice crops in this system.

We studied nutrient management for cotton - green gram - rice during 1991 - 92. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. The soil at the site represents the tract and is a sandy clay loam with low available N, medium P, and high K. Short-duration cotton variety SVPR 1 was sown during Apr 1991, and the second crop, green gram KM2, was grown during Sep 1991. This was

Crop yields in a cotton-rice system in Srivilliputtur, Tamil Nadu, India, 1991-92. ^a

Treatment			Yield (t/ha)		
Cotton 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha	Pulse 25-50-0 kg NPK/ha	Rice 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha	Cotton	Green gram	Rice
Full NPK	Full NP	Full NPK	0.78	0.33	4.1
N	Full NP	Full NPK	0.74	0.33	4.0
N	P	Full NPK	0.74	0.32	4.0
N	No fertilizer	Full NPK	0.75	0.24	3.8
No fertilizer	No fertilizer	Full NPK	0.49	0.23	3.8
Full NPK	No fertilizer	Full NPK	0.77	0.26	3.9
No fertilizer	No fertilizer	Full NPK plus preen gram stubble	0.50	0.23	4.2
LSD (0.05)			0.06	0.03	ns

^a ns = not significant.

followed by IR20, which was transplanted in Nov 1991 with different fertilizer levels.

There was a clear response when NPK was applied to cotton and green gram under rice - fallow conditions. Cotton yields with 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha and 60 kg N/ha alone were similar. In the succeeding green gram, the yield was higher when 25 kg N and 22 kg P/ha were applied, which was on par with 22 kg P/ha

alone. In this sequence, the rice crop had a uniform application of the recommended dose of NPK fertilizers. Rice yield was not affected by fertilizer treatments in the preceding crops.

These results indicate the significance of the recommended 60 kg N/ha for summer cotton, 22 kg P/ha for a pulse crop, and NPK for a wet-season rice crop in the cropping system studied (see table). □

Fertilizer management—**organic sources**

Breaking seed dormancy in *Sesbania rostrata*

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Sesbania rostrata has potential as a leguminous green manure for lowland fields in many countries. But its thick,

hard seed covering can cause problems for growers.

We tested several methods to break seed dormancy using hot water, sulfuric acid, scrubbing with sand, and scrubbing and soaking in hot water.

Scrubbing seeds with sand for 5 min and/or soaking in hot water (about 60 °C) for 15 min were not very effective.

Treating seeds with concentrated H₂SO₄

Germination of *S. rostrata* seed under different treatments.

Treatment	Observation (no.)	Germination rate (%) ^a
Control	4	12.00 ± 3.61
Hot water for 15 min	4	17.25 ± 2.77
Scrubbing with sand for 5 min	3	12.33 ± 1.70
Scrubbing + hot water	3	20.00 ± 2.94
H ₂ SO ₄ concentrated	7	94.39 ± 4.06
Fast washing	3	6.13 ± 0.72
Slow washing	3	15.67 ± 1.88
H ₂ SO ₄ diluted	3	

^a Mean ± standard error.

symbionts, *A. azollae* (AS-K₄) and (AS-S₁), and two free-living blue-green algae, *Anabaena* sp. (FL) and *Nostoc* sp. (FL), in calcium alginate on ammonia excretion and its influence on the growth of IR64 rice seedlings.

These N₂-fixing algal cultures were grown in IRRI N-free liquid medium for 2 wk in a growth room at 26 ± 1°C with 2000-3000 lux light intensity.

Suspensions were prepared from these cultures and mixed with an equal volume of calcium alginate aqueous solution (2.4%). The N content before immobilization in alginate was 2.96% for AS-K₄, 2.91% for AS-S₁, 3.14% for *Anabaena* sp., and 3.64% for *Nostoc* sp. Using a 10-ml pipette, the mixture of algal suspension in calcium alginate was added drop by drop to a solution containing 50 mM calcium chloride, resulting in the formation of round beads (Fig. 1). The algal beads were washed thoroughly, set on IRRI N-free medium, and incubated under the same growth room condition as the culture. Using Nessler's reagent method, we then measured ammonia excretion from the filtrate of the medium in which the algal beads had been maintained for 2 wk.

Nostoc sp., *A. azollae* (AS-K₄), *A. azollae* (AS-S₁), and *Anabaena* excreted 52.57, 34.28, 27.40, and 19.14 µg ammonia/m per 100 ml medium, respectively.

Forty IR64 rice seedlings that had been raised in sterile sand culture were maintained in a plastic cup. They were inoculated with 80 immobilized alginate algal beads (about 4,500 algal cells/algal bead). Sterile water was added and kept at a depth of 2.5 cm for 5 wk under controlled conditions. The seedlings were then carefully pulled out. Root, shoot growth, fresh biomass, and N

2. Effect of alginate-immobilized algal symbionts of azolla and free-living blue-green algae on growth of IR64 rice seedlings.

content were all significantly increased when plants were inoculated with alginate-immobilized algal beads. Inoculation with immobilized algal beads significantly increased the N content in IR64 rice seedlings over the control. N content ranged from .528% (*A. azollae* [AS-S₁]) to .588% (*Nostoc* [FL]) in the immobilized algal inoculated plants, and was .392% in the

control. Algal beads immobilized with *Nostoc* sp. produced the best seedling growth (Fig. 2).

The results showed that the immobilized algal symbionts of Azolla and free-living blue-green algae can continuously excrete ammonia that can be absorbed by rice seedlings and used in their growth. The cost of alginate beads at 5 kg/ha is \$7.5. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Antagonistic Soil bacteria for biological control of rice sheath blight (ShB) disease

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We explored the possibility of using antagonistic soil bacteria for biological control of ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn. We isolated bacteria from samples collected from areas covering four administrative divisions in Bangladesh. We tested 523 bacteria by placing two organisms in the plate

medium (dual culture method); 19.3% were antagonistic to varying degrees toward *R. solani* in vitro. Among these, 15% were fluorescent and 85% were nonfluorescent types.

Six bacteria were further tested for antagonism by dual culture and sclerotia dipping methods (Table 1). Isolate IS-

28 °C, after which they were kept in a humid room with an automatic mister at the same temperature for 12 d before the disease was assessed.

This method requires only a small amount of spore suspension (1×10^5 conidia/ml) and gives a panicle infection frequency of nearly 100%.

Smear inoculation produces a higher BI score and BI index than spray inoculation, but lower than injection inoculation (see table).

The new method is suitable for inoculation at 0-10 d after heading, but is especially suitable at 0-3 d after heading (see figure). □

Comparison of inoculation methods to induce neck BI in rice panicles in vitro. Hangzhou, China, 1990.

Variety	Infection frequency (%)			BI score ^a			BI index ^b		
	Injection	Smear	Spraying	Injection	Smear	Spraying	Injection	Smear	Spraying
<i>Panicles in vitro</i>									
Jiannongzao 9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Zhe 852	12.5	10.0	0.0	0.5	0.4	0.0	5.0	3.2	0.0
Erjiufeng	100.0	100.0	60.0	6.5	6.1	2.5	72.0	68.0	28.0
Zhefu 802	100.0	100.0	80.0	8.3	6.1	5.8	92.0	68.0	64.0
Yuanfengzao	100.0	100.0	100.0	9.0	5.4	6.8	100.0	60.0	76.0
Guangluai 4	100.0	100.0	100.0	9.0	7.9	6.5	100.0	88.0	72.0
<i>Panicles in vivo</i>									
Jiannongzao 9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Zhe 852	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Erjiufeng	100.0	85.7	18.2	7.2	2.3	0.4	80.0	25.7	6.2
Zhefu 802	88.9	72.7	66.7	5.2	3.6	4.5	57.8	40.0	49.3
Yuanfengzao	100.0	84.7	70.0	8.3	5.4	4.5	92.5	60.0	50.0
Guangluai 4	100.0	92.9	72.7	9.0	7.2	5.0	100.0	80.0	56.4

^a Based on Standard evaluation system for rice.

^b Disease index = $\frac{\sum (\text{no. of panicles with a given score} \times \text{value of that score})}{\text{total no. of panicles} \times \text{value of the highest score}}$

Effect of plant extracts on in vitro growth of rice blast (BI) pathogen *Piricularia oryzae*

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We tested 15 plant extracts for their effect on the growth of BI pathogen *P. oryzae*. Filtrates were taken as either a cold water or a hot water extract. For the cold water extract, fresh leaves were ground in sterile distilled water at 1:1 wt/vol with mortar and pestle and strained through a muslin cloth. For the hot water extract, leaves were immersed in water at 1:1 wt/vol, heated to 80 °C for 10 minutes, and then ground with a mortar and pestle.

To prepare the ethanol extract, we ground 100 g of leaf material in 100 ml of 95% ethanol. The homogenate was filtered through muslin cloth and the filtrate was evaporated at laboratory temperature ($30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). The residue was then dissolved in 100 ml of sterile distilled water.

The three extracts were heated separately to 45-50 °C for 10 minutes to eliminate contamination. Another cold water extract, prepared as described above, was also autoclaved at 20 lb pressure. We then added 2 ml of the four preparations to 18 ml of apple agar

medium in sterile petri dishes, and spread the extracts on the agar surface by rotation. With a sterile cork borer, we punched an 8-mm fungal disc from a 7-d-old culture of *P. oryzae*. The disc was placed in the middle of the petri dishes. The dishes were incubated at room temperature ($28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). Control treatments contained only inoculated apple agar medium. When the fungal growth in control dishes touched the periphery 12 d later, we measured the diameter of the colony for the respective treatments.

To assess biomass production, we added 8-mm fungal discs to flasks containing Richard's broth and 5 ml of the cold water extract of the plants. The

control contained only broth. We obtained the biomass 10 d after incubation at $28 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ by filtering the medium through Whatman no. 1 filter paper. The biomass was dried at 105 °C in a hot air oven for 48 h and then kept in a desiccator until constant weight was obtained.

Radial growth and biomass production were significantly reduced by extracts of all 15 plant species tested (see table). Cold water, hot water, and ethanol extracts inhibited the fungus better than the autoclaved extracts did. *Prosopis juliflora*, *Adhatoda vasica*, and *Vitex negundo*, which are commonly available on farms, showed the maximum inhibition. □

Effect of plant extracts on the growth of *P. oryzae*.^a

Plant species	Inhibition of radial growth ^a compared with control				
	Cold water extract	Hot water extract	Ethanol extract	Extract autoclaved	Biomass production
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	87.4 b	80.3 a	89.1 b	65.1 a	89.7 b
<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	35.0 h	28.4 f	34.5 h	20.4 e	42.5 h
<i>Antigonon leptopus</i>	4.8 i	3.7 h	3.6 k	2.4 g	4.1 i
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	66.5 d	61.6 b	71.5 c	60.2 ab	60.8 d
<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i>	6.1 i	6.2 g	7.3 ij	4.8 g	5.7 i
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	46.1 f	43.6 de	47.3 fg	22.8 de	45.9 g
<i>Datura metel</i>	5.5	4.9 gh	9.6 i	8.6 f	6.0 i
<i>Ipomea carnea</i>	46.8 f	40.4 e	43.0 g	27.2 d	41.6 h
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	48.1 f	49.3 c	52.1 e	47.1 e	47.3 g
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	40.3 g	46.1 cd	49.6 ef	42.8 c	51.9 f
<i>Phyllanthus fraternus</i>	53.3 e	43.5 de	47.9 efg	48.4 c	46.6 g
<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i>	64.5 d	44.1 de	68.4 d	55.8 b	55.2 e
<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	93.3 a	78.5 a	92.1 a	62.7 a	100.0 a
<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	4.2 i	3.0 h	6.7 j	4.2 g	5.4 i
<i>Vitex negundo</i>	72.4 c	64.5 b	73.3 c	55.2 h	71.4 c

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b In a column, means followed by common letters are not significantly different at 5% by DMRT.

Percent of leaves damaged by LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* on different rice varieties in valleys of the hilly regions of UP, India, 1991 kharif.

Valley	Variety	Av leaf damage (%)
Gagas Valley (1,100 m asl) ^a	Govind	85
	Pant Dhan 6	72
	VL-16	80
	Local	55
Garur Valley (1,200 m asl)	Govind	86
	VL-16	85
	VLK39	78
	Local	62
Someswar Valley (1,350 m ad)	Govind	77
	Pant Dhan 6	65
	VL-8	72
	Local	45
Bageswar Valley (1,000 m asl)	Govind	65
	IR24	72
	Saket 4	60
	Local	48
Chaukhtutia Valley (1,000 m asl)	Govind	78
	IR24	70
	Saket 4	82
	Local	54

^am asl = meters above sea level.

were reared in the laboratory for identification.

The insects appeared in July and remained until October. Infestation peaked from early Aug through late Sep. Average leaf damage was 45-86%. High-yielding dwarf varieties suffered more damage than local tall varieties (see table). Such a high LF incidence in the region's irrigated transplanted rice had not been recorded for 15-20 yr.

The Department of Plant Protection and Agriculture organized a campaign to control LF in infested areas. Chlorpyrifos 20 EC and monocrotophos 40 EC sprayed at 0.5 liter ai/ha gave effective control. □

Assessing the prevalence of rice pests in Cambodia

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Current information on the prevalence of insects and diseases in Cambodia is scanty. In 1990, the Cambodia-IRRI Rice Project sponsored in Phnom Penh a training course on problem diagnosis in rice. After the course, the 90 participants collected insect and disease baseline data in 261 fields in 12 provinces.

Using a zigzag sampling pattern, they examined 15 hills/field. For each hill,

they assessed disease severity (%) and insect injury (%) and estimated insect number by sweepnet. Prevalence was calculated as the proportion of fields in which specific diseases, insects, or beneficial arthropods were found, expressed as a percentage of the total number of fields visited. All fields were visited once from tillering to milk grain stage, and 102 fields were visited a second time from booting to ripening. The stage at which observations were made could not be standardized because of asynchronous planting and the difficulty of visiting fields.

Nearly 80% of the fields sampled were planted to traditional rice varieties, the most common being Phka Khney (8.0% of fields). IR36 and IR42 were the dominant modern varieties, respectively occupying 10.3 and 7.6% of the surveyed fields.

Brown spot (BS) was the most prevalent disease followed by narrow brown spot (Table 1). BS incidence, based on the number of infected tillers, was high in all provinces and in all varieties throughout the crop growth stages. BS was severe in variety Chhmar Prom during the first observation. The widespread occurrence and high incidence of BS may be due to poor plant nutrition, which is a

predisposing factor for the disease.

In most provinces, green leafhoppers (GLH) and brown planthoppers (BPH) were most prevalent during the first observation, followed by spiders and beetles (Table 2). In Takeo and Kompong Speu Provinces, there were more GLH on Phka Khney and IR50 varieties and at tillering to booting stages; more BPH were seen in Svay Rieng Province and on traditional varieties. Spiders and beetles were present throughout crop growth, but in low numbers.

Damage caused by hispa, cutworms, rice gall midge (GM), rice leaffolder, and stemborers was common in most provinces (Table 2). GM damage generally declined from tillering to milk grain stage in contrast to that of hispa, which gradually increased from tillering to flowering in the first observation. Percent insect damage generally increased with growth stage in the second observation, but in general, the insect population and damage were lower in the second observation than in the first observation.

We reported only pest prevalence and not incidence or severity of pest attack because we could not calibrate the

Table 1. Prevalence of rice diseases in provinces of Cambodia, 1990 wet season.

Province	Fields (no.)	Prevalence (% of fields)						
		Brown spot	Narrow brown spot	Bacterial blight	Bacterial leaf streak	Leaf blight	Leaf scald	Sheath blight
<i>First observation</i>								
Banteay Meanchey	10	50.0	20.0	30.0	20.0	60.0	0.0	10.0
Battambang	15	80.0	13.3	6.1	0.0	33.3	0.0	0.0
Kandal	76	34.2	1.3	10.5	10.5	1.3	2.6	0.0
Kompong Cham	10	100.0	20.0	40.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Chhnang	9	88.9	22.2	0.0	11.1	11.1	0.0	0.0
Kompong Speu	16	100.0	6.2	0.0	6.2	6.2	0.0	0.0
Kompong Thorn	10	30.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Phnom Penh	41	92.7	24.4	2.4	12.2	9.8	0.0	9.8
Prey Veng	11	63.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Pursat	3	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Svay Rieng	15	33.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Takeo	45	84.4	20.0	6.7	2.2	11.1	0.0	0.0
<i>Second observation</i>								
Battambang	9	88.9	55.5	11.1	0.0	22.2	0.0	0.0
Kandal	15	11.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Cham	5	100.0	20.0	80.0	40.0	40.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Chhnang	2	0.0	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Speu	13	38.5	30.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Phnom Penh	10	90.0	50.0	0.0	30.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Prey Veng	5	100.0	60.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Svay Rieng	6	83.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Takeo	20	100.0	0.0	20.0	0.0	30.0	0.0	0.0

1. Frequency of sprays. Leyte, Philippines, 1991 wet season.

2. Yield and number of insecticide applications by farmers in Leyte, Philippines, 1991 wet season.

would increase rice yields. Yield data, however, did not show any positive relationship with farmers' spray applications (Fig. 2).

Clearly, farmers tend to overestimate the damage they expect from leaf-feeders. They are extremely averse to risk and respond by spraying. Our challenge is to find ways to reduce or eliminate these unnecessary early spraying for leaf-feeding insects. □

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Relative potency of three insecticides on *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* and brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*

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Insecticides are detrimental to both natural enemies and pest species. Many entomologists argue that insecticides with selective toxicity for pest species would be useful. We evaluated three insecticides commonly used in rice for relative potency on BPH and its egg predator *C. lividipennis*.

We anesthetized 1-d-old female adults of both species with CO₂ and treated them with 0.5 pl of diluted doses of chlorpyrifos and BPMC using an Arnold microapplicator. Mortality was observed 24 h later. Eight batches of 10 insects each were used for each dose. For the molting inhibitor buprofezin, last-instar nymphs in 6 batches of 10 each were used because the chemical has little effect on adults. In all cases, control insects were treated with acetone. The data were subjected to probit analysis using D. Finney's computer program.

The probit lines fit the data well in all cases except for buprofezin on *C. lividipennis* (Table 1). At the concentration of 300 ppm, only 30% mortality was observed, and the probit analysis program estimated the LC₅₀ to be >900 ppm. Regression, however, was not significant.

Probit lines for BPMC and chlorpyrifos were parallel. Data were inadequate to carry out parallel analysis for buprofezin. The estimated relative potencies for the three insecticides are given in Table 2.

Chlorpyrifos and BPMC were 2.75 and 1.25 times less toxic to *C. lividipennis* than to BPH. In the case of BPMC, the relative potency ratio was not significantly different from unity,

temperature because in a previous study BPH mortality increased sharply at 40 °C.

We removed five randomly selected cages from the chamber at intervals and recorded mortality. A similar treatment at room temperature was used as the control.

The quantal response data obtained were subjected to probit analysis using a computer program developed by D. Finney. The median lethal doses (LT₅₀ expressed in hours) were estimated and compared (see table).

The wolf spider was the most tolerant of 40 °C; only 10% mortality occurred after exposure for 200 h. We were thus unable to estimate the LT₅₀, which was likely to be >280 h.

Regressions for BPH and *C. lividipennis* were significant. The slopes were significantly different and the two probit lines were clearly not parallel.

We estimate the wolf spider to be five times more tolerant of high temperatures than BPH. These differences may not affect the BPH-spider relationship and their range overlap would probably remain.

C. lividipennis, however, is extremely susceptible to high temperatures. The response is very homogeneous, as shown by the steep slope of the probit line. BPH is at least 17 times more tolerant of 40 °C than *C. lividipennis*. This implies that global warming might result in a

Mean effective doses (LT₅₀) of macropterous BPH females, *C. lividipennis* females, and *P. pseudoannulata* females exposed to 40 °C.

Insect	LT ₅₀ (h)	Fiducial limits	Slope
Macropterous BPH	47.3	38.6 - 72.1	3.4
<i>C. lividipennis</i>	2.8	2.5 - 3.0	11.0
Wolf spider	>280	Regression not significant	

disruption of this predator-prey relationship, and the range dissociation could lead to reduced egg predation.

C. lividipennis, however, is present in regions where temperatures often reach 40 °C and more tolerant populations may in fact exist. Temperature increases will also be gradual. This will allow more tolerant populations to be selected. □

***Hydrellia wirthi* Korytkowski damage to rice in Colombia**

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Rice leaf miner *Hydrellia* spp. are sporadic and minor rice pests in Latin America. But in Colombia, farmers are reporting an increase in the incidence of the pests and are spraying insecticide to control them twice per season, despite little information on the insect damage-yield relationship.

In Colombia, early weed control coincides with *Hydrellia* spp. infestations. Farmers in many Latin American countries use propanil for weed control. Propanil interacts with insecticides. To avoid phytotoxic effects, farmers must decide whether to control the insects or the weeds.

In fear of losing their crops, farmers often apply insecticides without scouting the field for eggs or larvae. In most cases,

however, damage is restricted to isolated areas in the field where plant density is low or where depressions that hold water attract adults.

We initiated a study to correlate damage by *H. wirthi* with reductions in rice yield. We used widely grown cultivar Oryzica 1, which farmers considered to be susceptible to *Hydrellia* spp. damage.

Oryzica 1 was direct seeded at 100 kg seed/ha. A water layer was established 5 d after plants emerged and was maintained for 15 d. Plants were inspected daily for egg oviposition or damage.

To observe oviposition, we marked 1-m² plots in the experimental area. All plants inside the plot were counted and inspected for eggs and/or miners. We considered a plant affected if it had one or more *H. wirthi* miner. Affected plants ranged from 0 to 100%. Control plots were selected from areas with no *H. wirthi* oviposition or damage. To eliminate any hidden insects, we sprayed plots with

Pearson's correlation coefficient for the relationship between *Hydrellia wirthi* damage and rice yield and plant height.^a

Parameter	Correlation coefficient	P>F
Yield	-0.18	0.4381 ns
Plant height	0.10	0.6606 ns

^ans = not significant.

insecticide 15 d after oviposition started. Plots were inspected weekly to detect other pests. Plant height was recorded at maturity. Plant height and yield were correlated with percentage of damaged plants.

The statistical analysis indicated no correlation between yield, plant height, and insect damage (see table). This agrees with results from other countries where *Hydrellia* spp. have little effect on rice yields. Although the damage looks alarming to farmers, plants recover when infested at early stages of plant development. □

Blower-Vac: a new suction apparatus for sampling rice arthropods

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Entomologists commonly use the D-vac suction sampler, available in different models, for quantitative studies of insects in rice and other habitats. This equipment however, is costly (Model 24 [backpack])

Arthropod catches from 4 suction devices.

Arthropods	Mean ^a			
	D-vac (backpack)	D-vac (hand-carried)	FARMCOP	Blower-Vac
Hemiptera	59.6 (23.7)	25.7 (10.8)	96.4 (32.9)	124.0 (34.9)
Hymenoptera	13.7 (6.3)	7.3 (2.5)	4.0 (1.6)	4.4 (2.4)
Coleoptera	7.5 (3.1)	2.6 (2.5)	8.7 (3.0)	8.3 (3.0)
Diptera	28.8 (6.6)	23.8 (9.6)	57.3 (41.9)	32.4 (23.0)
Orthoptera	4.5 (4.4)	0.7 (0.4)	4.6 (2.2)	3.6 (3.3)
Lepidoptera	0	0	0	0.1 (0.1)
Odonata	0.4 (0.3)	0.2 (0.2)	0.2 (0.2)	0.4 (0.4)
Araneae	11.8 (4.5)	4.9 (2.0)	14.1 (4.4)	12.4 (2.9)
Total	125.9 (40.5)	65.1 (19.8)	185.1 (56.5)	185.6 (45.7)

^aSE at 95% CL in parentheses.

Water management

Agricultural drought analysis for Hazaribagh, eastern India

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Drought at various phenological stages adversely affects upland rice. Qualitative and quantitative information about drought intensity, however, is not available for the subhumid, drought-prone tropics found in eastern India.

We characterized drought according to duration and severity at different rice growth phases by analyzing historical meteorological data (1913-91) from the Soil Conservation Research and Demonstration Farm, Hazaribagh. An estimation of annual drought was based on long-time mean and standard deviation. Years were classified as those with excess rain and slight, significant, severe, and disastrous drought.

To arrive at an estimation of agricultural drought, water deficit (rainfall – potential evaporation) between the 22d and 43d wk of the year (154 d) was considered (agricultural activities are confined to this period). We followed the methodology developed by Thomthwaite based on the Universal Hydrologic Equation to determine weekly water balance. Cumulative deficiency denoted drought severity.

The probability of drought occurring at different phases of the upland rice crop grown in the area was analyzed. Drought during the first 7 wk (28 May-15 Jul) is termed initial; that during the 8th wk in the middle of the season (16 Jul-9 Sep), intermediate; and that during the last 7 wk of the main growing season (10 Sep-28 Oct), terminal.

Evaporation records were available for 1972-91. Agricultural drought intensities differed for initial, intermediate, and terminal drought in all years except 1980, 1984, and 1991,

Agricultural drought duration, classification of yearly drought, annual and seasonal rainfall, maximum continuous drought duration and severity, Hazaribagh, India, 1972-91.

Year	Weeks of drought in the season				Type of drought Year	Rainfall (mm)		Maximum continuous drought duration (wk)	Maximum rainfall (mm)
	Total	Initial	Intermediate	Terminal		Annual	Cropping season		
1972	15	4	4	7	Severe	907.1	819.9	9	218.61
1973	10	6	2	2	Slight	1091.2	1013.1	4	174.72
1974	10	5	2	3	Slight	1263.4	1140.1	5	177.30
1975	14	6	3	5	Severe	1014.5	850.0	4	188.50
1976	15	7	3	5	Excess rainfall	1344.5	1228.4	7	271.58
1977	9	2	2	5	Excess rainfall	1781.2	1439.4	4	98.35
1978	8	4	1	3	Excess rainfall	1679.7	1506.7	3	77.16
1979	12	3	3	6	Significant	1078.5	957.0	6	96.96
1980	7	2	0	5	Excess	1366.4	1288.7	4	125.50
1981	9	3	1	5	Severe	949.8	782.5	4	176.52
1982	11	4	1	6	Significant	1149.1	965.5	6	230.01
1983	8	4	1	3	Significant	1159.5	963.3	2	88.44
1984	8	2	0	6	Excess rainfall	1603.0	1486.3	5	135.70
1985	10	4	3	3	Slight	1090.3	1041.0	4	192.66
1986	12	3	5	4	Slight	1073.0	1017.0	3	150.14
1987	11	5	1	5	Slight	1270.0	1152.0	5	95.35
1988	12	3	3	6	Significant	1086.6	962.4	3	130.55
1989	9	2	3	4	Significant	1057.5	985.5	4	77.81
1990	7	2	2	3	Excess rainfall	1465.5	1297.0	3	32.33
1991	9	4	0	5	Excess rainfall	1431.2	1278.6	3	103.77
Mean	10.3	3.75	2	4.55		1198.2	1108.7	4.4	149.99
SD	2.43	1.48	1.38	1.36		364.0	218.2	1.64	67.40

Probability (%) of drought occurrence

Probability of drought occurrence for continuous periods of 0-7 wk at given crop stages, Hazaribagh, India, 1972-91.

when intermediate drought did not occur (see table). Two spells of terminal drought occurred during 1991, with 3 wk with 79.55 mm total rainfall and 2 wk with 24.12 mm rainfall.

The probability of up to 7 wk continuous drought occurring at the selected phases of the main cropping season is

shown in the figure. At the initial crop phase, a drought of 2-4 wk duration is more likely to occur. This signifies the prevalence of agricultural drought or soil moisture deficit during the early vegetative phase. Higher intensity droughts (3-6 wk duration with corresponding severity) are more prevalent toward the

efficiency were determined for each combination of parameters.

All the tested parameters showed statistical interrelations. Efficiencies were highest at high static heads, slower speeds of rotation, with three rollers attached and with a clearance of 8 mm. The power required to rotate the pump increased with number of rollers, speed of rotation and static head, and with decreasing clearances.

The tube materials differed greatly in durability and performance. Efficiencies for neoprene tubing were about 30% at a high head, but at low speeds of rotation, its durability was drastically reduced due to bulging and finally bursting of the hose at the pump exit. An unused polyester-reinforced tube proved to have a much longer lifetime, even at low speeds and

high static heads. The number of rollers and the clearance, however, had significant effects on the self-priming abilities of this tubing.

With two rollers attached, a clearance of 9 mm, and a rotation speed of 36 RPM, the pump was self-priming even at a head of 10.53 m, but efficiency was drastically reduced by back-flow. With four rollers, the chemical hose was unable to self-prime. At an efficiency of about 36%, a maximum power of 59.8 W was needed to operate the pump with three rollers attached, a clearance of 8 mm, and 24 RPM to deliver about 11 liters/min to a head of 10.53 m. We predict that a stream flow of about 0.7 m/s can provide the required power of 60 W to drive this pump if attached to an

undershot waterwheel with an efficiency of 20% and a paddle surface area of 1 m²,

The efficiency of the pump decreased under the same experimental conditions to about 10% with an input power requirement of about 50 W. The polyester-reinforced chemical hose survived 1 million cycles of tube compression and self-restitution in a durability test at a static head of 10.53 m. This is equivalent to about 600 h or 25 days of continuous field operation at 10 RPM and three rollers. Ideally, a tube material with the combined flexibility of the neoprene tubing and the durability of the polyester-reinforced hose is needed.

An achieved efficiency of about 30% at high heads, combined with reduced power requirements at low rotation speeds, indicates the potential of the peristaltic pump. □

Front and half-section views of peristaltic pump with 3 sets of rollers.

ENVIRONMENT

Relationships among methane emission from flooded ricefields, solar radiation, straw incorporation, and yield

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Many questions exist about potential physiochemical changes in the atmosphere due to increased methane emissions from rice plants growing in flooded soil. We assessed some of the key factors influencing methane production and emission from typical silty-clay rice soils near Beaumont, Texas. We grew the cultivar Jasmine 85, which matures about 140 d after emergence from Apr plantings, under

conventional drill-seeded culture during 1990. We maintained 10 cm of water from about 30 d after emergence to about 10 d before harvest. We took weekly duplicate 30-min methane samples from 0.4-m² open-bottom chambers with rims that rested below the water surface.

Methane flux determinations showcu significant methane emission of at least 100 mg/m² per d through rice plants, beginning about 10 d after soil flooding.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A prototype simulation model to investigate the spread of tungro (RTD) viruses in a rice crop

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RTD causes major losses in tropical lowland irrigated rice production. Key questions relating to the management of the disease remain unanswered. These include the relative importance of primary disease spread into plantings and secondary spread within plantings; the role of individual vector species; the importance of different infection sources; and the impact of control options, such as insecticide application, removal of diseased plants, and use of resistant varieties. We are developing a simulation model of the epidemiology of RTD within a rice crop to help improve RTD risk assessment, evaluate management tactics, and identify research targets.

We have developed a prototype model that simulates virus infection dynamics

based on a set of provisional assumptions about virus and vector biology (see table). The prototype, intended to stimulate feedback from field scientists, has revealed several information gaps, such as rates of vector movement, virus acquisition, and virus transmission.

The model simulates the position and infectivity status of the vectors and the corresponding RTD infection pattern in a grid of 2,500 rice hills over 60 d.

As an illustration, the figure compares model output at 60 d after transplanting (DT) for two very simplified vector immigration situations:

a. *All immigrants infective.* Five vectors transmitting RTD spherical virus only, and 20 transmitting both spherical and bacilliform viruses, all entering the crop at 10 DT, at random positions.

b. *With additional noninfective immigrants.* As in (a), but with 100 noninfective vectors also entering the crop at 10 DT at random positions.

The greater potential for secondary virus spread in situation (b) causes an increase in the rate of disease progress (keeping in mind that this is a prototype model). We are planning a quantitative

evaluation of the potential impact of RTD management options over a range of disease development situations. □

Provisional structure and assumptions for a prototype simulation model for the spread of tungro viruses in a rice crop.

Rice	2,500 hills of an RTD/vector susceptible variety in a square grid. Each hill can be infected with either spherical or bacilliform viruses, or with both, or be uninfected.
Vectors	10,000 (maximum) <i>Nephotettix virescens</i> , allowing simulations of a single vector species at low densities (up to an av of 4 adults plus nymphs/hill).
Vector immigration	Mix of any infectivity status at my arrival time from 1 to 60 DT.
Adult age at immigration	3 d with any virus infectivity acquired the previous day.
Vector development (days after oviposition)	Egg hatch = 10, adult moult = 25, first oviposition = 30, last oviposition = 34, death = 36.
Population growth of the vector	Development is incremented daily. Population dynamics simplified with fecundity = 8 eggs/female and juvenile mortality = 0, giving effective growth rate of 4 per generation.
Vector movement	
Frequency:	4 times/d with a probability of movement between hills of 0.5 (adults) and 0.1 (nymphs).
Direction:	Random.
Distance:	Nymphs: 1 hill (100%) Adults: 1 hill (40%), 2 hills (30%), 3 hills (20%), 4 hills (10%).
Virus retention	3 d for both nymphs and adults for each virus.
Virus acquisition rate (per vector)	Probability of 0.5 after 6 h on an infected hill (but bacilliform virus is acquired only when spherical virus is present, or after access to spherical virus).
Virus transmission rate (per vector)	
Spherical virus:	Probability of 0.1 for an infective vector after 6 h on a hill.
Bacilliform virus:	Probability of 0.5 for an infective vector after 6 h on a hill (but bacilliform virus is transmitted only when spherical virus is present or after access to spherical virus).
Latent period	7 d (rice), 0 d (vector).

Simulated position and virus infectivity of vectors (left) and the pattern of infection of rice hills (right) at 60 DT; a) with all immigrants infective, and b) with additional noninfective immigrants.

Communication and Publications Services, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines. Please specify the tape format and system desired. □

IMI moves

The International Mycological Institute (IMI) has a new address beginning 1 Oct 1992:

International Mycological Institute
Bakeham Lane,
Egham, Surrey
TW20 9TY
England
Phone: 0784 4701 11
Fax: 0784 470909

New Thai ministers of agriculture and cooperatives announced

The new director-generals of the Thai Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives are

Mr. Montri Rumakom

Director-General
Department of Agriculture
Bangkok 10900

Dr. Sittilarp Vasuwat

Director-General
Department of Agricultural Extension
Paholyothin Road
Bangkok 10900

Mr. Nar-ong Minanandana

Director-General
Land Development Department
Paholyothin Road
Bangkok 10900

Mr. Sawad Wattanayagorn

Director-General
Royal Irrigation Department
Samsen Road
Bangkok 10900

IRRI announces series on rice research

Rice science in the 1990s is fast-paced and challenging. To keep agricultural policymakers, educators, and others up-

to-date in rice and related sciences, the International Rice Research Institute is initiating the *IRRI information series*.

"The series is designed to keep the world abreast of research and technological advances at the Institute. It highlights IRRI's contributions to science and development that are improving the lives of the billions of people for whom rice is the staple food," says Dr. Klaus Lampe, IRRI director general. The new series focuses on how IRRI scientists are addressing specific problems in each of the rice ecosystems, and how they are enhancing sustainability and productivity through

collaborative research and training with colleagues in the national agricultural research systems.

Challenges and opportunities in less favorable ecosystems: Rainfed lowland rice is the first booklet in the series. Subsequent issues will describe IRRI's work in the upland rice ecosystem, deepwater and tidal wetlands rice ecosystems, molecular biology, integrated pest management, training, and genetic resources.

Copies of the booklet are available at no charge from the Communication and Publications Services, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines. □

NEWS ABOUT RESEARCH COLLABORATION

Mechanizing rice production in Madagascar

Farmers and local manufacturers in Madagascar responded enthusiastically to demonstrations of IRRI-designed hydrotilters, threshers, and harvesters conducted recently by technicians and a consultant from the USAID-funded Madagascar-IRRI Rice Research and Training Project.

The island of Madagascar produces about 2.4 million t of rice and imports some 100,000 t every year. Rice production is partly constrained by the shortage of labor for land preparation, transplanting, harvesting, and threshing during peak seasons. Weed control

problems and high grain losses during threshing also contribute to rice production problems.

Upland farmers in the middle west have shown interest in owning harvesting and threshing machines, whereas farmers from the irrigated and rainfed lowland expressed interest in the threshing equipment.

IRRI has extended technical assistance to local manufacturers to produce prototypes of these machines, and Madagascar manufacturers have requested blueprints for other machines, such as the spinning brush, very low-volume pesticide applicator, and small and medium ricehull stoves. □

Rice genetic evaluation expands in Africa

The International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice (INGER) in Africa has expanded its rice improvement work from focusing only on the irrigated rice ecosystem to include the rainfed and upland ecosystems.

INGER trials have been successful in identifying adapted, stable, and high-yielding rice varieties for Africa in

addition to screening varieties for stresses.

INGER-Africa initiated a collaborative rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) nursery in 1988. INGER-Africa also conducts research on the African rice gall midge and supports the research of the National Cereals Research Institute, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, and West Africa Rice Development Association. Several national agricultural research systems

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